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Microscopic strength of silicon particles in an aluminium–silicon alloy

M.G. Mueller*, M. Fornabaio, G. Žagar, A. Mortensen

Laboratory of Mechanical Metallurgy, Institute of Materials, École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL), Station 12, CH-1015 Lausanne, Switzerland

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ABSTRACT

A microscopic three-point bending test that measures the strength of faceted particles of high aspect ratio is developed and used to probe individual coarsened plate-like silicon particles extracted from the eutectic Al–12.6%Si alloy. Focused ion beam milling is used in sample preparation; however, the tapered beam cross-section and multistep preparation procedure used here ensure that the particle surface area subject to tension in mechanical testing is free of ion beam damage. Results show that coarsened silicon particles in aluminium can reach strength values on the order of 9 GPa when they are free of visible surface defects; such high strength values are comparable to what has been reported for electronic-grade silicon specimens of the same size. By contrast, tests on eutectic silicon particles that feature visible surface defects, such as pinholes or boundary grooves, result in much lower particle strength values. Reducing the incidence of surface defects on the silicon particles would thus represent a potent pathway to improved strength and ductility in 3xx series aluminium casting alloys.

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1. Introduction

The link between the microstructure and the mechanical properties of aluminium–silicon (AlSi) based alloys is a subject that has been investigated extensively for several decades [1–15] because it is both relevant and broad. It is relevant because more than 90% of today's aluminium castings are based on AlSi, a binary system which provides for excellent castability at low cost, leading it to be widely used, for example in the automotive industry [16]. The subject is broad because the properties and morphologies of engineering AlSi alloy microconstituents can be varied greatly with alloy composition, and with casting and heat treatment procedures [4–6,8,17–25]. The subject is also interesting because aluminium–silicon alloys are, together with metal matrix composites, an attractive model system for the study of damage and fracture in two-phase ductile–brittle materials [1,3,6,7,10,26–28].

In the simplest case, namely a binary AlSi alloy, the microstructure consists of a ductile aluminium matrix reinforced with brittle silicon particles. These two phases are also the main (but not the only) phases in more chemically complex 3xx series aluminium casting alloys. In most of these alloys, the fracture of silicon particles plays a dominant role among the various factors that determine the alloy's deformation and fracture properties

[3,5–7,15,21,24,25,29–36].

Yet, little is known of the intrinsic strength of Si particles within aluminium [37,38]. To date, the strength of silicon particles in AlSi alloys has been assessed mainly by indirect methods. These evaluate average properties of the silicon phase by taking measurements on the alloy and then interpreting data via a model that links properties of the inclusions with those of the alloy.

The strength distribution of silicon particles has in this way been estimated by coupling dispersion hardening models, which were used to calculate the average stress in the particles from macroscopic alloy flow properties, with a measurement of the volume fraction of broken particles, which was produced using light microscopy along polished sections of tensile samples [8,30,39]. Caceres et al. [30] and Wang et al. [8] calculated in this way a Weibull reference strength of 3 GPa for eutectic silicon particles having a 4 μm representative diameter in heat treated A356 and A357 alloys. The strength of the particles was widely distributed, however, given that particle fracture was observed to begin at (average estimated) particle stresses of about 500 MPa. Using the same approach, Kiser et al. [39] estimated 215 MPa as an average strength of the Si phase, without discrimination of primary from eutectic silicon particles, in the form of coarser particles within a hypereutectic Al–20Si alloy heat-treated to the T4 condition. In an investigation on the plastic deformation of A356 and A357 alloys with and without Sr-modification, Wang [9] estimated the average tensile stress on the silicon particles as a function of the alloy plastic strain. Their results show a change in the shape of the curve at a

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: martin.mueller@epfl.ch (M.G. Mueller).

particle stress level in the range of 600–800 MPa (depending on the particle aspect ratio). This was associated with the onset of particle cracking and matrix plastic relaxation.

Huber et al. [10] developed a void nucleation and growth model using a near-eutectic, Sr-modified, AlSi alloy with silicon particles of shape near that of a spheroid. In the model, void nucleation was attributed to fracture of the silicon particles and the critical stress value for particle fracture in the model, or in other words the average strength of the particles, fitted the experiments with a value of 550 MPa. In a comparatively early work, Coade et al. [1] used a X-ray diffraction technique to measure the average strain of the silicon particles in a sodium-modified A356 alloy submitted to bending. The strain was used to estimate the average stress in the particles and the fracture stress of the particles was estimated to be 230 MPa. It is noteworthy that, as the authors state in the paper, such a fracture stress would imply surface cracks 2–4 μm deep on the particles, which is admittedly inconsistent given that the particles size was also on that order. Along the same line, in a more recent work Finlayson et al. used a neutron diffraction technique during tensile testing to measure the average strain in the silicon particles of Sr-modified A356 alloys heat treated to T4 and T6 conditions [38]. To evaluate the strength of the silicon particles, a macroscopic applied plastic strain of only 0.01 was considered (strains larger than that were claimed to yield too large uncertainties), which resulted in average particle stress values of 220–330 MPa. At that level of applied plastic strain only 1–2% of the particles would be fractured, which makes this assessment a strength estimate of only the weakest particles in the alloy [38].

All studies cited in the previous paragraphs require a micro-mechanical model to deduce the stress on the Si particles either from the measured composite stress or from the measured average Si particles lattice strain. This in turn raises two issues, namely (i) the validity of approximations made in constructing the micro-mechanical models, and (ii) the fact that such models give a value for the average stress exerted on the particles, which may differ significantly from the stress exerted on those particles that fracture at a given point of the composite's deformation history. As a result, precisely when and why silicon particles in AlSi alloys fracture is at present still poorly understood. Measuring locally the strength of individual silicon particles can provide direct insights into the matter; however such a measurement is a significant challenge that has only been reported in a couple of studies.

One approach that has been proposed to achieve this is based on the micro-Raman technique [35,40], specifically a method developed by Narayanan et al. [41], which allows to relate the shift of the silicon peak in the Raman spectrum with the in-plane stresses of a (111) silicon wafer. Applying this on silicon particles in a AlSi alloy thus requires a well-polished surface of bending [40] or compression [35] test samples of the alloy, along which a silicon particle identified as having a (111) orientation can be spotted. The main drawback of this approach is that the particle on which the stress is measured is affected by polishing, which introduces defects (scratches) on the particle. With this technique, Joseph et al. found that eutectic silicon particle fracture occurred at stresses in the range 500–1000 MPa, whereas Harris et al. reported a value of 600 MPa. Another approach to the direct measurement of alloy particle strength was described by Riahi et al. [42], where the strength of silicon-rich intermetallics in a modified AlSiFeCu-NiMgMn alloy was measured by means of an instrumented scratch test conducted on a surface of the alloy. The particles, protruding relative to the aluminium matrix by a few micrometres after a surface deep-etch, were bent to fracture by the sliding indenter. The approach, however, was not applied to silicon particles (to the best of our knowledge).

In summary, the strength of the silicon phase in AlSi alloys has

been mostly assessed using approaches that measure averaged back-calculated phase properties, and differences in measured strength values have been interpreted in terms of average geometrical and morphological features of the Si phase such as size, aspect ratio and interconnectivity. Reasons why Si particles are as strong or as weak as they are found to be, or in other words structure/property relations in these particles viewed as a material with its own strength-limiting defects, have not yet been explored in depth. In the present work, we probe the local strength of eutectic silicon particles individually by means of a microscopic three-point bending test, results of which give direct measurements of individual particle strength. We use the method on particles where no defects are noted and also on particles containing observable defects, and we measure thereby the effect of such flaws on their strength.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Method

The flexural strength of plate-like silicon extracted from a binary AlSi alloy is measured in this work using a microscopic three-point bending test conducted on particles that are removed from the alloy by selective leaching the aluminium matrix. Prior to leaching, the alloy is heat-treated to coarsen the particles; this causes them to adopt naturally a variety of plate-like shapes showing flat surfaces oriented along (111) planes of the Si crystal [43–46]. We use one such flat surface, as it presents itself after etching, as the probed surface subjected to peak tensile stress during the bend test.

The sides of the specimens are shaped by focused ion-milling to turn the particles into straight beams amenable to bend testing; this inevitably causes material in the corners of the lower beam surface to be altered by the ion beam. In early measurements conducted with beams that had parallel sides and rectangular cross-sections, we found that fracture surfaces can betray crack initiation at, or near, the beam corner, i.e. from a portion of irradiated and gallium-implanted material which is likely not to be representative of silicon as it is within the alloy (Supplementary Information gives an example of such a fracture surface). This problem was alleviated by giving the beams a trapezoidal (tapered) cross section, with the wider side of the beam subjected to tension during the test. This alters the stress distribution, causing tensile stresses to decrease as one approaches the edge of the beam. Fig. 1 illustrates this by showing results of finite element simulations, conducted as described below, on two beams: one with a near-rectangular cross section and the other with a cross section typical of tests conducted here. As seen, whereas in the former the first principal stress is uniform along the X axis, in the latter the stress at the mid-span edge is 10% lower than the peak stress and decreases rapidly in the Z direction. This is representative of all specimens tested in this work: the minimum difference in computed stress between the edge and the peak stress in the centre was always between 10% and 20%. With such trapezoidal beams, thus, the region of the samples that is exposed to peak values of applied tensile stress during the test does not include material that was altered by focused ion beam milling, which is situated along the sidewalls of the sample. This is an important feature of the present test method, which we describe in more specific detail in the following sections.

We note in passing that such trapezoidally tapered specimens are often used in fracture toughness testing; however, in such tests the taper is oriented the other way around (i.e. with the narrower end at the location of peak tensile stress). This is practiced where crack growth stability is sought, since in this orientation, as the crack advances, its front broadens, decreasing the driving force.

Fig. 1. Illustration of the difference in the maximum principal stress distribution between a rectangular (left) and a trapezoidal (right) cross section three-point bending specimen (cut view through mid-span plane). In this work, the design with trapezoidal cross section was used to keep the higher maximum stresses away from the edges of the beam, which are affected by ion milling.

This is ultimately exploited in the well-known Chevron-notch fracture toughness test first introduced by Barker [47], developed into standards [48] and recently used to measure fracture toughness at microscopic scale [49–51]. By contrast, in this work we aim to measure strength and accept the fact that the taper will, in the present orientation, accelerate crack growth once incipient cracks become unstable.

2.2. Material

The silicon particles probed in this work belong to a commercially pure near-eutectic AlSi alloy that was first produced as a cast ingot by Alusuisse Technology & Management AG (Neuhausen am Rheinfall, Switzerland). Chemical analysis provided along with the alloy gives 12.6 ± 0.4 wt. % Si, with 0.033 ± 0.002 wt. % Fe as the main impurity and <0.003 wt. % of Cu, Mn, Mg, Cr, Ni, Zn and Ti. The as-received alloy microstructure largely consists of lamellar Al–Si eutectic containing interconnected silicon plate-like particles, plus small amounts of (i) relatively equiaxed and larger primary silicon particles, (ii) primary α -aluminium dendrites and (iii) pores.

This alloy was heat-treated for 7 days at 550 °C to coarsen and disconnect from each other the eutectic silicon plate-like particles,

Fig. 2. Optical micrograph of the heat-treated near-eutectic AlSi alloy used in this work. Inset: SEM image of a few eutectic silicon particles such as the ones probed in this work after selectively etching the aluminium phase to expose them.

which as a result became also somewhat more regular in shape, Fig. 2. Silicon particles were then extracted from the alloy by selectively dissolving the aluminium matrix for 1 week at room temperature in a solution prepared using H_3PO_4 85%, CH_3COOH 100% and HNO_3 70% mixed in volume ratio 83:5.5:5.5. The solution containing the extracted silicon particles was then filtered using qualitative filter paper grade 413 (VWR International bvba, Leuven, Belgium). Particles captured on the filter paper were rinsed several times, first with water, and finally with ethanol. The particles were then recovered within ethanol from the filter paper and were, in this wet condition, spread over a flat polished quenched K990 steel substrate of hardness 950 HV/100 (Böhler International GmbH, Vienna, Austria). The ethanol quickly evaporated, leaving dry silicon particles lying on the steel substrate.

2.3. Test specimen preparation

The bend specimen preparation method is summarized in Fig. 3. The steel substrate with silicon particles resting along its surface was introduced in a Zeiss™ NVision™ 40 (Oberkochen, Germany) dual beam (SEM/FIB) instrument. One or a few plate-like particles were selected (Fig. 3a) and shaped as a beam by 30 kV Ga^+ Focused Ion Beam (FIB) milling. To produce its trapezoidal cross section, the sample was tilted so that the angle between the FIB and the top surface of the particle was 70° to mill one side of the particle (Fig. 3b) and 110° to mill the other side (Fig. 3c). The FIB currents used ranged from 3 nA in initial rough-milling steps down to 80 pA in the last milling steps, notably to finish the sides of the beam.

Once each silicon beam was milled, a carbon FIB-induced deposit was applied to weld the beam to a micromanipulator needle (Fig. 3d). The beam was then lifted (Fig. 3f) and deposited onto a rectangular hole previously dug elsewhere by FIB milling the surface of the steel substrate (Fig. 3e). Thin carbon welds were then made to (gently) fix the silicon beam to the substrate (Fig. 3g) before releasing the silicon beam from the needle; this was done by FIB milling the weld holding them together (Fig. 3h).

A typical specimen ready for testing, prepared from the eutectic particle in Fig. 4a, is shown in Fig. 4b. Note that, in this process and in this testing configuration, the particle surface that will later be subjected to tensile stress was never contacted by the FIB, and was furthermore protected, by the underlying steel, from being coated with redeposited matter while the beam was being machined.

Apart from the regular specimens just described, four specimens were prepared so as to subject to tension a surface along which a

Fig. 3. Scheme of the preparation of a microscopic three-point bending specimen from a silicon particle extracted from the AlSi alloy.

Fig. 4. (a) Eutectic silicon plate-like particle extracted from the AlSi alloy, lying on a steel substrate. (b) Microscopic three-point bending specimen (S8 in Table 1) ready to be tested prepared from the particle in (a). FIB milling, transportation with a micromanipulator and carbon FIB-induced depositing were used for the preparation; however, the bottom surface of the specimen is unaffected by these. Relevant geometrical dimensions are indicated on the image and on the inset. Bottom-view (c) and side-view (d) of the nanoindenter diamond tip used for the microscopic three-point bending tests.

flaw was spotted by SEM imaging; one such example is Fig. 5e. These four flaw-containing particles (Fig. 5a–d) had to be turned over before milling, such that their flawed surface was made to contact the steel surface before carving the three-point bend specimen. To achieve this, the particle was first welded to the micromanipulator needle with a carbon deposit. Then, the silicon particle was transported and welded to the edge of a stainless steel razor blade. The razor blade was next extracted from the SEM/FIB instrument, flipped upside-down by hand, re-introduced in the microscope, the silicon particle rewelded to the micromanipulator needle, separated from the blade, transported and placed along the steel substrate. Thereafter, it was machined with its defect-containing surface contacting the steel, following the procedure described above and summarized in Fig. 3.

2.4. Testing procedure

Micrometric three-point bending tests were conducted, using a TI 950 TriboIndenter® (Hysitron® Corporation, Minneapolis, MN, USA) nanoindentation apparatus, on the machined beams resting over a square hole cut into the steel substrate. To this end, the steel substrate with the FIB-prepared specimen(s) was first mounted on top of a rotation-tilt stage (Newport Corp., Irvine, CA, USA) that was

fixed on the nanoindenter positioning stage. Parallelism between the tip and the specimen was achieved within $\pm 0.5^\circ$ by iteratively making a shallow indent in the steel substrate, scanning the indent with the Scanning Probe Microscope (SPM) of the NanoDMA™ transducer and correcting the tilt with the rotation-tilt stage. Once parallelism was achieved, the bend tests were carried out using the 3D OmniProbe™ transducer in displacement control mode at 60 nm/s. Load was applied up to fracture, with 1–4 partial unloading/reloading sequences in-between. The nanoindenter probe that was used to conduct these three-point bend tests was a diamond probe custom-shaped by FIB-milling to feature, at its tip, a cylindrical ridge with a diameter of $\sim 1.5 \mu\text{m}$ and a length of $\sim 8.5 \mu\text{m}$, Fig. 4c–d.

3. Results

3.1. General response

A representative measured load–displacement curve is shown in Fig. 6. Initially, up to a displacement of $\sim 250 \text{ nm}$, the signal is ill-defined and features a few load drops. This portion of the curve is likely a signature of specimen accommodation and of the thin carbon welds on the side of the bent silicon beam being chipped off

Fig. 5. (a–d) Eutectic silicon particles extracted from the AlSi alloy featuring distinctive surface defects: a small pore in (a), a larger pore in (b), a deep trench-like interface in (c) and a shallow stepped interface in (d). These particles were turned over before producing a three-point bending specimen out of each, to probe the strength of their defect-containing surface. One such specimen (S11 in Table 1) is shown in (e); it was prepared from the particle in (c). Image (f) is the fractured half-beam and fracture surface after the three-point bending test of the specimen in (e). The fracture origin in (f) is indicated with a white arrow.

Fig. 6. Typical measured load–displacement response of a microscopic three-point bending test of the silicon specimen shown in the inset (specimen S1 in Table 1). Responses calculated by finite element modelling with rigid supports (long-dashed line) and with elastic supports (short-dashed line) are also shown (corresponding to the models in Fig. 7a and b respectively).

(see Fig. 5f, which shows craters along the sides of a beam where the welds were located). This interpretation is suggested by the observation (e.g. Fig. 4b and Fig. 5e) that the specimen and steel substrate preparation procedure tends to leave a gap of some tens or hundreds of nanometres between the specimen and the substrate. After this first transient regime, the load increases steadily with displacement, at first with an increasing slope (a signature of indentation effects) and then linearly, suggesting that the deflection is now dominated by bending of the beam. This steady-slope loading curve then continues up to a maximum force F_{\max} followed by a sudden load-drop and a jump in displacement, which evidently corresponds to fracture of the bending beam. The curve in Fig. 6 shows also a partial unloading–reloading cycle, which was

conducted starting from a load near 6 mN in the range of displacements between 400 and 500 nm: the slight difference in slope between this and the monotonic loading curve shows that some irreversible deformation takes place during loading. In some specimens, this difference was more pronounced: these were specimens with greater amounts of powder-like material along their surface (see for example Fig. 5b and f). Separate observations in the SEM (not shown here) of indented locations where such fine particulate material covered silicon particle surfaces show that this layer of nanoscopic powder-like particles deforms plastically under the indenter, explaining, together with some possible plastic deformation of the silicon under the indenter, the slightly increased compliance upon initial loading of the sample.

3.2. Stress analysis and sensitivity analysis

Each individual three-point bending specimen was analysed by means of a bespoke quasi-static three-dimensional Finite Element (FE) model using Abaqus/Standard™ 6.11 software (Dassault Systèmes, Providence, RI, USA), Fig. 7. The indenter was modelled as a cylindrical rigid analytical surface of diameter 1.5 μm. The dimensions of each silicon bending beam (h , b_1 and b_2) and of the corresponding hole in the steel defining the span S were obtained from SEM images of each sample, in place before testing. Despite the careful FIB-machining procedure (Fig. 3), small deviations from symmetry in the geometry of silicon bending specimens were unavoidable. When such deviations were noted, they were neglected and the specimens were assumed to be symmetric.

It is known that the large facets of plate-like Si particles in aluminium are {111} planes and that the particles contain multiple {111} twins parallel to their large facets [43–46]. Here, simulations were run using linear elastic constants $C_{11} = 165.6$ GPa, $C_{12} = 63.9$ GPa and $C_{44} = 79.5$ GPa [52] and assuming that the silicon beams are single crystals free of twins with [111] in the Y direction (Fig. 7). The (unknown) orientation of the silicon beam

Fig. 7. Finite element models of the microscopic three-point bending test on silicon particles (Specimen S1 in Table 1). The model in (a), where the supports are rigid surfaces, was used to obtain the maximum first principal stress of each tested specimen. The model in (b), where the supports are elastic, was used to analyse the influence of various possible misalignments. The stress field shown in (a) is the first (tensile) principal stress in GPa. The values are the largest at the centre of the bottom surface and decrease towards the edges in the X-direction as a consequence of the tapered cross-section.

axis (i.e. the Z direction in Fig. 7), on the other hand, was arbitrarily chosen since the (111) plane in diamond cubic crystal structures is elastically isotropic [53].

In finite element modelling, two alternatives were used for the steel supports that define the span: (i) rigid analytical surfaces (Fig. 7a), and (ii) isotropic linear elastic material of Young's modulus 210 GPa and Poisson's ratio 0.3 (Fig. 7b). As for the geometry of the support, in both cases the edge was filleted with a radius of 150 nm. In Fig. 6 the load–displacement responses resulting from these two models are indicated in dashed lines. The response is obviously more compliant when the support is considered to be elastic; however, when the peak load is reached, the difference in maximum first principal stress value for the two configurations is less than 1%. Given this negligible difference and the fact that the model with rigid analytical surfaces (Fig. 7a) is computationally far less demanding, this type of model was implemented and used in data interpretation of the ensemble of samples tested here.

The model with elastic supports (Fig. 7b) was nevertheless used to investigate numerically the influence of possible misalignments using the specimen in Fig. 6. Separate simulations were run with misalignments having magnitudes that represent extreme cases of reasonable experimental imprecision, namely: (i) the indenter rotated 5° about the Y axis (i.e. beam axis and indenter ridge not perpendicular); (ii) the supports rotated 5° about the Y axis (i.e. beam axis and support edges not perpendicular); (iii) the indenter rotated 2° about the Z axis (i.e. loss of parallel contact between the indenter and the beam); and (iv) the indenter off-centre by 1 μm in the Z direction (i.e. lateral misalignment). Results show that for cases (i), (ii) and (iii) the maximum first principal stress varies by less than 2%. Only for Case (iv) is the influence more important: for 1 μm of lateral misalignment the calculated maximum first principal stress at F_{\max} is 5% lower than with a well-aligned sample. This type of misalignment was therefore also simulated for the specimen with the shortest span (specimen S5 in Table 1), this being the

Table 1

Dimensions (S to α), experimentally measured force at fracture (F_{\max}) and calculated flexural strength by Simple Beam Theory (σ_{SBT}) and by Finite Element analysis (σ_{FE}) of microscopic three-point bending tests of plate-like eutectic silicon particles extracted from the AlSi alloy. Specimens marked with (*) are ones that probe particles containing visible flaws.

Specimen ID	S [μm]	h [μm]	b_1 [μm]	b_2 [μm]	α [$^\circ$]	F_{\max} [mN]	σ_{SBT} [GPa]	σ_{FE} [GPa]
S1	10.6	3.0	2.8	5.4	113	22.7	9.3	8.7
S2	9.7	2.2	2.6	4.7	116	14.9	11.5	10.9
S3	11.8	4.5	2.0	5.6	112	33.8	7.2	6.6
S4	11.8	4.2	1.6	5.0	112	23.4	6.5	6.0
S5	7.1	2.3	0.9	2.9	113	14.1	13.2	11.9
S6	11.8	3.5	1.6	4.6	113	14.5	6.1	5.7
S7	10.6	4.5	2.1	5.8	112	50.8	9.1	8.3
S8	9.5	2.8	0.9	3.6	116	11.6	8.6	8.0
S9	9.5	2.7	1.4	3.6	113	13.9	9.9	9.1
S10	7.4	2.0	1.2	3.0	114	7.5	9.3	8.7
S11 (*)	12.9	3.8	2.8	6.2	114	4.1	1.1	1.1
S12 (*)	9.5	3.8	2.4	6.0	116	22.6	5.0	4.7
S13 (*)	7.1	2.4	0.9	2.9	113	3.2	2.7	2.6
S14 (*)	7.4	4.3	0.8	4.5	113	18.8	3.9	3.6

sample most affected by lateral misalignment; here, a $1\ \mu\text{m}$ misalignment leads to an error slightly lower than 10%. An interesting observation in running these calculations was that in all cases of misalignment (in particular for the lateral misalignment) the simulation predicted a *lower* peak stress at a given load than it did for the perfectly centred and aligned system. We therefore take these sources of error as being ones that lead to *overestimate* the peak stress within the sample when it is calculated using the bespoke finite element model knowing the peak load F_{\max} that is reached when it fractures.

The friction coefficient μ in the models was taken as 0.2 both for the beam-supports [54] and the beam-indenter contacts. To evaluate the influence of this parameter, simulations were run for several specimens also with $\mu = 0.1$ and 0.3. Results show that the maximum first principal stress at F_{\max} does not change by more than 5% compared to the result with $\mu = 0.2$.

Also the sensitivity to possible errors in the determination of dimensions was evaluated by running simulations for the specimen in Fig. 6 varying widths b_1 and b_2 , height h and span S , one at the time, by $\pm 5\%$. Results indicate that such errors in width and span lead to approximately $\pm 5\%$ error in the resulting maximum first principal stress at the load of fracture, whereas $\pm 5\%$ error in the determination of the height h leads to approximately $\pm 10\%$ error in the computed stress.

Summarizing the results of the sensitivity analysis described above, we conclude that misalignments can overestimate the calculated strength value of a specimen by at most 10%, that uncertainty in the friction coefficient can lead to a $\pm 5\%$ error and that errors in the measurement of dimensions lead to a $\pm 10\%$ uncertainty in the computed particle strength. Pooling results of these calculations, we deem reasonable to consider that strength values reported here could be overestimated by up to about 15% and underestimated by up to about 10% of the reported values. Those are therefore the magnitudes of the error bars used in Fig. 8.

3.3. Measurements and test results

Three-point bending tests were carried out on ten specimens such as that in Fig. 4b, whose bottom surfaces—the surfaces subjected to the maximum tensile stress—were not observed before testing. *A priori*, not having observed signs of defects along the sample sides before or after ion-milling, these can be assumed to be free of large flaws (as data later confirm, see below). An additional four tests were conducted using specimens that contained a clearly

Fig. 8. Flexural strength (evaluated as the maximum first principal stress calculated from the finite element model of each specimen) versus the specimen effective probed area for “regular” three-point bending specimens (black dots) and for specimens produced with a visible defect along the lower beam surface (hollow squares). The error bars are +10% and –15%, which is an estimate of the pooled uncertainty arising from the sensitivity analysis (see main text). Strength of electronic grade silicon as reported by Namazu et al. [69] is shown with lines indicating 10%, 63% and 90% of failure probability. Inset: Weibull fit of regular specimens.

identified defect along the tested surface, Fig. 5a–d. These required identification of the defect along the upper, visible, surface of the Si particle, followed by an operation in which the samples were turned over before being carved and tested with the flaw on their lower surface (see Section 2.3).

Measurements and results are collected in Table 1. Here, the flexural strength is evaluated at F_{\max} using two calculation schemes: (i) the maximum first principal stress calculated from the bespoke FE model of each specimen assuming rigid supports (σ_{FE}), or (ii) Simple Beam Theory (σ_{SBT} , see below).

After testing, fractographic analysis was in general not possible because all but the weakest specimen (S11 in Table 1, shown in Fig. 5e) could not be found after fracture along the steel substrate. In some cases, small debris was found scattered around the test site, whereas in other cases no remaining portion of the specimen could be found at all. In fact the only fractured half-beam that could be found after testing (Fig. 5f) was situated approximately 600 μm away from the test site. These observations suggest that, for all but one sample, the specimens shattered into a few or many small pieces that were dispersed upon fracture by the sudden release of the elastic energy stored within the samples.

4. Discussion

4.1. Flexural strength of the silicon plate-like particles

The particle flexural strength is evaluated as the calculated maximum first principal stress at the experimentally measured load at fracture. This means that Mode I failure is assumed throughout this work. Resulting values of σ_{FE} are plotted in Fig. 8, using uncertainty bars corresponding to +10% and –15%, this being an educated approximation based on the analysis of uncertainties

detailed above, versus the effective area A_{eff} that was subjected to tensile stress in the sample in question, defined as follows on the assumption that the particle strength is governed by Weibull statistics.

In plotting the data in terms of A_{eff} (Fig. 8), we implicitly assume that fracture is only caused by surface defects. Moreover, in what follows we also assume that fracture only occurs from the bottom surface of the beams, i.e. we neglect the possibility of fracture occurring from their sides (this assumption being motivated by the fact that the bending beams have a trapezoidal cross section, see Fig. 1). Along this line of thought, one can seek whether the present bending strength data can be expressed in terms of the two-parameter Weibull cumulative distribution function [55], according to which the probability that a bent sample breaks at or before reaching an arbitrary reference stress σ_r is given by

$$P(\sigma_r, A_{\text{eff}}) = 1 - \text{Exp}\left(-\frac{A_{\text{eff}}}{A_0} \left(\frac{\sigma_r}{\sigma_0}\right)^m\right) \quad (1)$$

where

$$A_{\text{eff}} = \iint_{\sigma_1 > 0} \left(\frac{\sigma_1}{\sigma_r}\right)^m dA \quad (2)$$

is the effective area, calculated by integrating the tensile component of the first principal stress σ_1 over the surface subjected to tension (i.e. over the bottom surface) to the power of m . Here, the Weibull modulus m and $A_0\sigma_0^m$ are two independent material parameters. Defining a “Weibull stress” $\sigma_W = (A_{\text{eff}}\sigma_r^m)^{1/m}$ (note that the units of σ_W are $([\text{length}]^2[\text{stress}]^m)^{1/m}$) and correspondingly $\sigma_{W0} = (A_0\sigma_0^m)^{1/m}$, Eq. (1) can then be recast as

$$P(\sigma_W) = 1 - \text{Exp}\left(-\left(\frac{\sigma_W}{\sigma_{W0}}\right)^m\right) \quad (3)$$

In using the stress field at the load of fracture from the finite element simulations to interpret data, we insert $\sigma_r = \max(\sigma_1) = \sigma_{FE}$ into Eq. (2), and we assign a fracture probability to each experiment using the probability estimator function $P_i = (i-0.5)/N$, where $i \in [1, \dots, N]$ is the ranked specimen index and N the total number of specimens. With this, we numerically solve the associated maximum likelihood problem to calculate m and σ_{W0} .

Weibull parameters are estimated in this way using data from Specimens S1 to S10 in Table 1 (i.e. excluding particles selected for identified defects), giving $m = 5.86$ and $\sigma_{W0} = 12.41 (\mu\text{m}^2\text{GPa}^{5.86})^{1/5.86}$; the fit is shown as an inset in Fig. 8. Note that this Weibull modulus must be viewed as highly approximate given the small sample size (10 tests) and the assumptions made in the analysis. Nevertheless, it is a reasonable value for a brittle material, which in turn allows estimating on a reasonable basis the magnitude of the effective surface area being probed in these experiments. From this result it follows that, if the average A_{eff} is taken as the characteristic area A_0 , i.e. $A_0 = 7.1 \mu\text{m}^2$, then the characteristic strength σ_0 equals 8.8 GPa.

Strength values measured with the ten samples that were not selected for the presence of a given defect (Samples S1 to S10, filled circles in Fig. 8) show a significant scatter range but invariably reach very high values of peak stress upon fracture: bending strengths vary between about 6 and 12 GPa. Scatter in the value of the samples' bending strength has two obvious potential sources, namely the statistical distribution (in size and in shape) of flaws that act as the origin for fracture, and the directional anisotropy of the fracture toughness of monocrystalline silicon [56–59].

These measured strengths far exceed fracture stress values that have been either estimated using mean-field methods or measured

directly on silicon particles within aluminium: the literature review in the introduction shows that work to date has yielded values in the range from roughly 200–1000 MPa. Still, values measured here, although higher by more than an order of magnitude, are not outlandish. There have been a great number of measurements of the fracture strength in small-scale samples of (generally single-crystalline) silicon produced by lithographic methods or in silicon nanowires; a comprehensive review was recently written by Del Rio et al. [59]. Such samples give fracture strength values that have a marked dependency on sample size (e.g. Fig. 28 in Ref. [59] and Fig. 10 in Ref. [60]): the strength of relatively large specimens often lies in the range from 1 to 4 GPa (e.g. Refs. [61–68]) while as the specimen size becomes smaller, the fracture strength has been reported to exceed 10 GPa [69,70], at times significantly [71,72], approaching silicon's theoretical strength of 21–23 GPa along $\langle 111 \rangle$ tensile directions [73,74]. Noteworthy in the literature is the study by Namazu et al. [69], who produced and tested bend beams of similarly trapezoidal cross-section (this being a result of anisotropic wet etching) spanning a wide range of sizes. Their data were expressed in terms of Weibull strengths using the area-based expression in Eq. (1). Transposing their fracture statistics data to the present sample size ranges gives the three fracture probability lines in Fig. 8. As seen, present data are broadly compatible with the data of Namazu et al. [69].

To sum up, the present test data show that Si platelets tested for bend strength along plate surfaces, reach strength values consistent with what is measured in high-perfection single-crystalline silicon samples produced by deposition and etching processes typical of the Microelectromechanical Systems (MEMS) industry.

In contrast, the four specimens prepared from visible-flaw containing particles (Fig. 5a–d, specimens S11 to S14 in Table 1) gave strength values significantly lower than Specimens S1 to S10 (Table 1), Fig. 8. Among these four samples, the specimen containing the deep trench-like surface feature (Fig. 5e, likely a twin boundary groove or a line where two ridges limiting the growth of $\{111\}$ facets were blocked before coalescing) was the weakest; this was the only sample for which a half-beam was found after fracture (Fig. 5f). In this fractured half-beam it can be observed that fracture started at the defect and initiated away from the edges (white arrow in Fig. 5f). The fracture path then produced a zigzag surface towards the upper surface. This upper surface is a $\{111\}$ plane, which is known to be the family of planes with the lowest surface energy [57,75] and the easiest cleavage planes in silicon (followed closely by the $\{110\}$ planes in $\langle 110 \rangle$) [56–58,76,77]. Noting also that $\{111\}$ planes are 19.5° from each other, the walls of the trench and the zigzag planes of the fracture path are probably $\{111\}$ planes. In Fig. 5f one can also observe the chipping-off of material around the carbon weld bead, which occurred by locally breaking the silicon around the weld rather than along the carbon deposit-silicon interphase.

Having determined that microstructural defects at the surface of the plate-like silicon particles decrease considerably their strength, a statistical analysis of the occurrence of defects was carried out to have an insight into the possible relevance of such defects on particle fracture in the alloy. A total of 225 randomly selected plate-like silicon particles extracted from the alloy were examined in the SEM. The observable defects (i.e. surface defects on the SEM-accessible surface(s) of each particle) were classified into four types and it was then counted how many particles featured each type of defect. The result indicates that pores (e.g. Fig. 5a and b) are present in 32% of the particles, necks in 26%, trench-like interfaces (e.g. Fig. 5c) in 52% and step-like interfaces (e.g. Fig. 5d) in 12% of all examined particles, whereas no noticeable flaw could be observed in 30% of the particles. The results of this analysis shows that the majority of silicon particles within the alloy feature defects. Indeed,

roughly half of them feature one or more trench-like interfaces similar to that in the weakest specimen in Fig. 8.

The facts that silicon particles with defects are weaker –probably due to stress concentration effects– and that those occur in great numbers within the alloy is possibly what reconciles the silicon particle strength values measured in this work with the far lower strength values calculated by indirect means in previous work (reviewed in the introduction).

4.2. Re-evaluation using simple beam theory

We have used bespoke finite element models to evaluate the strength of each three-point bending specimen and to analyse statistically the results (see above); however, the testing method exposed here is obviously easier to implement if data can be interpreted using analytical methods. To explore whether this is a viable approach, in this subsection we revisit the data analysis using a rougher, straightforward approach based on Simple Beam Theory (SBT). We do so –despite the fact that specimens in this work can not be considered to be slender– to show that such a simple approach can also be used to evaluate data from three-point bending experiments on specimens with tapered cross-section such as those produced and tested here.

According to SBT, in a three-point bending configuration the maximum tensile stress occurs at mid-span and is $\sigma_{\text{SBT}} = M y/I$, where $M = F_{\text{max}} S/4$ is the applied moment at mid-span, $y = (h/3)(2b_1+b_2)/(b_1+b_2)$ is the distance from the neutral axis to the bottom surface and $I = (h^3/36)(b_1^2+4b_1b_2+b_2^2)/(b_1+b_2)$ is the moment of inertia about the axis that passes through the centroid of the trapezoidal cross-section in the X direction (see Fig. 4 for a definition of geometrical parameters in preceding expressions). As can be seen in Table 1, σ_{SBT} values for the tests in this work are between 3 and 11% higher than σ_{FE} values. In other words, using SBT in data analysis would lead to an additional error of the same sign (i.e. overestimation of the strength) and comparable magnitude as uncertainty arising from the various types of misalignment (Section 3.2).

As was done above using results of FE simulations, here too we can analyse strength data in terms of two-parameter Weibull statistics assuming that fracture is caused by flaws on the bottom surface of the specimens. In this case we take $\sigma_{\text{r}} = \sigma_{\text{SBT}}$, and $\sigma_1(z) = \frac{\sigma_{\text{SBT}}}{S^{3/2}} z$ as given by SBT. Replacing these into Eq. (2) leads to

$$A_{\text{eff}} = b_2 2 \int_0^{S/2} \left(\frac{\sigma(z)}{\sigma_{\text{SBT}}} \right)^m dz = \frac{S b_2}{m+1},$$

whereas the “Weibull stress” now reads $\sigma_{\text{W}} = (A_{\text{eff}} \sigma_{\text{SBT}}^m)^{1/m}$. The solution to the maximum likelihood problem of finding the Weibull parameters in Eq. (3) using data from Specimens S1 to S10 gives with this approach $m = 5.84$ and $\sigma_{\text{W}0} = 13.25(\mu\text{m}^2 \text{GPa}^{5.84})^{1/5.84}$. It follows that if the average A_{eff} is taken as the characteristic area A_0 , i.e. $A_0 = 6.8 \mu\text{m}^2$, then the characteristic strength $\sigma_0 = 9.5 \text{ GPa}$.

These results obtained using SBT compared to those obtained using the outputs of finite element modelling (Section 4.1) indicate that the estimated Weibull modulus is the same for both approaches, whereas the effective areas and the strength values are under- and overestimated, respectively, by only about 10% or less. Therefore, if one lacks the time or means to conduct bespoke finite element analysis to interpret tests conducted according to the procedure developed in this work, SBT provides rapid and simple access to relatively precise data.

4.3. Influence of the etching procedure

In this work, the surfaces of the silicon particles probed for

strength were not affected by focused ion beam milling; however, the potential effect of the etching procedure that was used in sample preparation has to be addressed.

When silicon is exposed to acidic media that do not contain fluorine ions, a nanometric passivating layer of silicon oxide forms immediately along its surface, thereafter preventing further oxidation [78]. Oxide layers ~1–3 nm thick have been measured for silicon immersed in aqueous HNO_3 solutions at room temperature and it has been furthermore determined that the thickness does not increase with time even under an applied anodic voltage of 5 V [79,80]. In phosphoric acid and in acetic acid, anodic voltages of a few or a few tens of V must similarly be applied to increase the oxide thickness on silicon [78]. In a study on surface treatments of a AlSiMg alloy it was determined that a short (2 min) exposure to phosphoric acid leaves silicon particles within the alloy unaffected, and that aluminium phosphate is not deposited on the particle surface, given that they are cathodic when compared to both the Al matrix and Mg_2Si particles [81].

Solutions based on a mixture of nitric, phosphoric and acetic acids, in similar proportions as in the etchant used here, are typical aluminium wet-etching solutions that have been used for decades in microfabrication [82–85]. Aluminium is known to be etched in these solutions through a two-step mechanism [83,84]: the nitric acid reacts with aluminium producing aluminium oxide, which is then dissolved by the phosphoric acid. The acetic acid buffers the solution and improves wetting. These solutions are known not to etch silicon microcomponents nor silicon oxide (or very slowly, even at 50 °C) [82,84,85].

Still, exposure times typical of microfabrication are much shorter than the 7 days used to extract particles tested in this work (note, however, that this is an upper limit of the time spent by the particles in contact with the solution, as silicon particles from the alloy were progressively exposed by the slowly advancing etching front). Therefore, in order to get an insight on the thickness of the oxide layer of the particles tested here in three-point bending, a TEM lamella was prepared using FIB milling, from a particle that had been subjected to the etching procedure used here to extract particles from the alloy. The observed oxide thickness was ~30 nm. In a study on fracture of silicon nanospheres of size in the order of 100 nm, Mook et al. [86] suggested that the thickness of the oxide layer around the nanospheres could account for the size of crack-initiating defects. Now, if we solve for strength σ in $K_{\text{IC}} = \sigma (\pi a)^{1/2}$, with $a = 30 \text{ nm}$ and $K_{\text{IC}} = 0.9 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$ as is typical of silicon [56,58,87], one obtains $\sigma \approx 3 \text{ GPa}$, which is below values of strength measured here for specimens without large flaws, i.e. specimens S1 to S10 (Table 1 and Fig. 8). This leads to conclude that the layer of oxide formed during etching did not govern the strength of the Si particles tested here, since measured strength values correspond to critical flaws even smaller than the oxide thickness. It is, on the other hand, possible that the oxide layer could have healed small cracks along the Si particle surfaces; however, the presence of such cracks along the surface of individual Si crystals is unlikely as they would be healed by Si diffusion along the Al/Si interface or through the aluminium phase during the Si particle coarsening heat treatment.

We thus deem the influence of larger flaws on the strength of the Si particles measured here to be representative of the behaviour of Si particles within the coarsened Al-12.6%Si alloy from which they were extracted.

We also studied the possibility that Si particle surface defects might have been produced by the etching procedure used in this work. To this end, we extracted particles from the alloy also by electroetching with sodium chloride and with nitric acid as electrolytes. We found no indication of a difference in the observable particle defects with etching procedure, giving confidence that the

observed defects are present originally in the silicon particles within the alloy.

5. Conclusion

A microscopic three-point bending test is developed to measure the flexural strength of hard reinforcing particles of high aspect ratio. Although focused ion beam milling is used in sample preparation, the particle surface probed in tension is pristine, in the sense that it is not affected by focused ion beam milling or by redeposition. This is achieved on one hand through the specific specimen preparation procedure and on the other hand through the use of a tapered bend beam cross section, which focuses the stress at the centre of the bottom surface of the bending beam while reducing it at the edges.

Bespoke finite element modelling is used to access the peak stress at fracture. Misalignment can lead to overestimate calculated strength values by at most 10%, the most critical source of error being deviations of the indenter placement point from the beam span centre. This level of error is of the same order as uncertainty resulting from error in sample dimension measurement. Alternatively, simple beam theory can be used to interpret data; this leads to overestimate by about 10% resulting strengths, largely as a consequence of the rather short span of the specimens.

Results on coarsened eutectic silicon particles extracted from Al-12.6wt.%Si show that:

- coarsened Si particles can be very strong, with a characteristic strength around 9 GPa when bend particles of effective surface area near $7 \mu\text{m}^2$ are tested; and that
- when such particles contain microstructural flaws, such as pin-holes and particularly trench-like interfaces along their facets, their strength is strongly diminished.

Given the high particle strength values that are recorded in the absence of such flaws, their elimination from Si particles in Al–Si alloys should be a potent pathway to strongly improved strength and ductility in 3xx series aluminium casting alloys.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data related to this article can be found at <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.actamat.2015.12.006>.

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